

THE USE OF TRICHLOROACETIC ACID FOR THE EXTRACTION OF PHYTIN OF FOODSTUFFS.

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A method for the estimation of the phytin content of foodstuffs is described, in which trichloroacetic acid is used for the extraction of phytin instead of the usual HCl extraction. It is suggested that the modification introduced in this paper is more suitable for determining the distribution of the acid-soluble phosphorus compounds in foodstuffs.

During the course of our investigations on the distribution of phosphorus compounds in various cereals both in the resting seed and during germination, the method of McCance and Middowson (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 2694) was followed for the estimation of phytin wherein $N/2$ HCl was used to extract the phytic acid. In order to obtain an accurate and strictly comparable data for the distribution of acid-soluble phosphorus compounds (*i.e.* labile phosphorus, total inorganic phosphorus, phytin phosphorus, etc.) it is necessary to carry out the estimations of all phosphorus compounds in the same extract, *i.e.*, in the trichloroacetic acid, which is generally employed for the extraction of acid-soluble phosphorus compounds except phytin. The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken with a view to finding out how far the values obtained by the trichloroacetic acid extraction method compare with those obtained by the usual HCl extraction method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Powdered cereal (25 g.) was extracted first with 20 c.c. of 10% trichloroacetic acid, in an ice-chest for about half an hour with occasional shaking and filtered, the filtrate being kept in the ice-chest. The sample was again extracted in the same manner with 20 c.c. of trichloroacetic acid and the filtrate from this was added to the first filtrate. The total extract was neutralised with $N/10$ -sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein and again slightly acidified with $N/10$ -acid and the total volume was measured. 20 C.c. of this extract were taken and made up to 50 c.c. in a volumetric flask and 20 c.c. aliquots were taken for the estimation of phytin. The rest of the procedure followed was exactly the same as that of McCance and Middowson (*loc. cit.*).

Phytin Content of Cereals as determined by the HCl-extraction Method and Trichloroacetic Acid Method.

The following table gives the values of phytin estimated by the usual HCl-extraction method and by the trichloroacetic acid method.

TABLE I.

The phytin content of cereals.

No.	HCl extraction method.			Trichloroacetic acid extraction method.	
	Total P.	Phytin P.	Phytin P.*	Phytin P.	Phytin P.*
1. Rice	0.355%	0.305%	86	0.308%	86.7
2. Rice germinated	0.328	0.230	72.3	0.251	78.6
3. Rice (another sample)	—	0.268	—	0.282	—
4. Ragi (<i>Elaeusine coracana</i>)	—	0.120	—	0.131	—
5. Bengal gram (<i>Cicer arietinum</i>)	—	0.100	—	0.125	—
6. Green gram (<i>Phaseolus radiatus</i>)	0.410	0.188	46	0.203	50.0
7. Green gram (germinated)	0.540	0.162	30	0.185	34.3

* as % of total P.

The Influence of Concentration of Trichloroacetic Acid on the Extraction of Phytin.

The effect of varying concentrations of trichloroacetic acid on the extraction of phytin was then investigated. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II.

Rice.

Total P.	Concentration of trichloroacetic acid used.	Phytin.
0.355%	2%	50%
"	5	74
"	10	73.7

The results show that 5-10% trichloroacetic acid is the optimum concentration for the extraction of phytin.

The Influence of Repeated Extraction on the Phytin Content of the Extract.

In the following table are presented the results obtained on the influence of repeated extraction on the phytin content of the trichloroacetic acid extract.

TABLE III.

Rice.

Total Phosphorus	1st extraction. Phytin P.	2nd extraction. Phytin P.
0.355%	0.277	0.006

The results show that practically the whole of phytin phosphorus is removed in the first extract. For all practical purposes, therefore, one extraction is enough to obtain the total quantity of phytin in the extract.

It is clear from the above results that the values obtained for the phytin content of cereals and pulses by the use of trichloroacetic acid as extractant compares favourably with those obtained by the HCl-extraction method. In some cases, however, slightly higher values were obtained by the trichloroacetic acid method which may be due to the efficient extraction of the phytin. It is suggested that trichloroacetic acid can replace HCl in the estimation of the phytin content of foodstuffs, particularly when the distribution of the acid-soluble phosphorus compounds in the same extract is to be determined.

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